

8. Interactive Mode

The interactive mode helps you to override version detection results for every port. Use the following argument to enable the interactive mode:

```
--script-args "vulscaninteractive=1"
```

9. Reporting

All matching results are printed one line. The default layout for this is:

```
[{id}] {title}\n
```

You may enforce your own report structure by using the following argument:

```
--script-args "vulscanoutput='{id} - Title: {title} ({matches})\n'"
```

Supported are the following elements for a dynamic report template:

Element	Description
{id}	ID of the vulnerability
{title}	Title of the vulnerability
{matches}	Count of matches
\n	Newline
\t	Tab

10. Disclaimer

Keep in mind that this kind of derivative vulnerability scanning heavily relies on the confidence of the version detection of nmap, the amount of documented vulnerabilities and the accuracy of pattern matching. The existence of potential flaws is not verified with additional scanning nor exploiting techniques.

11. Update 06/28/2013 14:00

Unfortunately, I have received an email today by representatives of Secunia. They do not allow me to include any references to Secunia advisories. This is why I had to exclude the Secunia vulnerabilities in secunia.csv from the current release 1.0.

12. External Links

- [1] https://www.computec.ch/mruef/software/nmap_nse_vulscan-1.0.tar.gz
- [2] <https://vuldb.com>
- [3] <http://cve.mitre.org>
- [4] <http://www.osvdb.org>
- [5] <http://www.securityfocus.com/bid/>
- [6] <http://www.securitytracker.com>
- [7] <https://www.scip.ch/vuldb/scipvuldb.csv>